

Impact of Corporate Governance Mechanisms on Profitability of Nigerian Listed Industrial Goods Companies

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the determinants that affect the profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. To conduct the empirical investigation, a descriptive research design was adopted where secondary data were extracted from annual published financial statements of the listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria as of December 31st, 2022 for the period of 2013-2022. The population of the study was the listed industrial goods firm in Nigeria. The sample size was determined based on the selection criteria of data availability and listed in the Nigeria Exchange Group. Data collected was analysed using multiple regression. The findings show that the combined effect of audit committee meetings, audit committee composition, and audit managerial share owner has a favourable and significant impact on financial performance for listed industrial goods businesses in Nigeria. As a result, the study suggests that audit committee meetings have a favourable and significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian-listed industrial goods corporations. The report advised that the government should invest extensively in the assets of large industrial goods corporations because larger industrial goods enterprises have a higher degree of profit and such businesses can readily take advantage of economies of scale to reduce costs and, eventually, profit.

Keywords: Audit Committee Composition, Managerial Share Ownership and Profitability.

JEL Codes: C23, C58, C87, M21, M24, M48

1. INTRODUCTION

With increased global rivalry, ensuring the longevity of every business organisation is a pressing issue in the business world. Excellent performance is regarded vital for corporate success in such a competitive environment (Adegbie & Adekoya 2022). Thus, the topic of firm performance has been a major focus for stakeholders all over the world, as business organisations exist to earn a profit on their investment (Acheampong et al. 2014). Profitability is thus a major metric of performance because commercial organisations are primarily concerned with profit and wealth maximisation. The business climate is becoming more competitive, and organisations are being compelled to increase their level of competencies and expand their skills in order to be more cost effective, creative, and competitive in the sector (Awan & Tahir, 2015).

Profitability is therefore a crucial indicator of performance because business organizations are primarily focused on maximizing profit and wealth (Ogunleye & Olokoyo 2019). Without profitability, a company would struggle to draw in investors and run its operations sustainably over the long term. According to Magaretha and Supartika (2016), business owners need to develop

strategies for achieving a reasonable level of profitability in a market that is competitive. Manager's and academics engage in significant debate on topics related to firm profitability and ways to increase it (Pratheepan, 2014).

The effectiveness of the business unit will increase as profit increases. Some researchers, including Asgari, et al., (2015), Burja (2011), Lobos and Szweczyk (2013), Saleem and Rehman (2011) claim that a number of factors, including the amount of leverage, which affects the firm's expense in terms of interest payments, firm size, liquidity, cash flows, corporate governance mechanisms like liquidity, and audit committee meetings, have an impact on profit (Awan & Tahir, 2015). Company's executive is responsible for using the appropriate tactics from time to time while taking into account various variables that could have a significant impact on the company's profitability. In Nigeria, audit committee meetings play a crucial role in ensuring transparency and accountability in listed industrial goods companies. However, determining the optimal frequency of meetings can be a challenge because too few meetings might lead to insufficient oversight, while too many may strain resources (Ujunwa, 2012). The balancing routine financial audits with special investigations or emerging risks requires careful consideration. Also, managerial share ownership can align the interests of executives with those of shareholders, but practical issues due constitute in determining the appropriate level of managerial ownership can be challenging where too little may result in a lack of incentive, while too much might lead to excessive risk-taking. And the timing of when executives can sell shares can impact their decision-making and long-term commitment (Saibaba & Ansari, 2012). Finally, the composition of the audit committee can be challenging to find individuals who possess the necessary skills and are also independent. Also, striking the right balance between independence and industry knowledge is critical. Committee members need to be independent enough to provide unbiased oversight, but they also need a good understanding of the industry to be effective (Fauzi & Locke, 2012).

Under the present government, industrial goods firms comprising businesses that participate in the heavy industry sector have been regarded as having the ability to spur economic growth. Companies that make industrial items help industrialization progress since their goods are still useful to industries (Akinmulegun, 2012). It is critical to assess the internal factors that influence these businesses' profitability because they are businesses that exist to generate a profit and whose survival is critically dependent on that ability (Adegbaaju, Ologunde, & Adegbaaju 2020). The drivers of profitability of industrial products enterprises, which are rapidly expanding due to rising demand, must be understood given the current administration's commitment to reviving the country's wave of industrialization.

Global industry and firms constitute majorly competitors, irrespective of the industry the firms are operating (Dogan, 2013). For a competitive advantage to be expanded, it is very essential for firms to highly utilize the benefits derived from their employee's productivity as a competitive instrument for success in achievement of organisation objectives (Sylvester & Nkiru, 2015). In order to remain in the market in the face of inconsistencies, organisations are concentrating more on activities within such as their employee productivity and the resources made available. Nigeria's industrial goods sector has recently been plagued by a slew of issues that have harmed its production and profitability (Akinmulegun, 2012). This is exacerbated by unfavourable macroeconomic conditions, which affect both business owners and consumers, but the

perseverance of Nigerian manufacturers has seen them manage these issues while hoping for better days (Adegbaju, Ologunde, & Adegbaju 2020).

Also, Nigeria faces significant challenges in terms of inadequate infrastructure, including power supply, transportation networks, and access to ports. These deficiencies can result in increased costs, delays in production, and difficulties in distributing goods (Siyanbola, Olaoye, & Olurin 2015). Frequent power outages and an unreliable electricity grid pose significant challenges for industrial goods firms. This leads to increased production costs due to the need for backup power generators, lower productivity, and hindered growth prospects. The inconsistency and frequent changes in government policies, regulations, and trade barriers can create uncertainties for industrial goods firms (Akinmulegun, 2012). Such unpredictability can make it difficult for businesses to plan long-term investments, adapt to changing market conditions, and hinder their competitiveness.

Despite the enormous number of research that have been undertaken in Nigeria, they are not sufficient for existing reliance as they exhibit a number of methodological flaws, the most intrinsically of which are the use of primary data when secondary information would have been preferable, the use of a breadth with a coverage period that is years behind, the abrupt selection of factors without the use of a scientific approach like stepwise regression, and the selection of a small number of firms from which it may be difficult to draw generalizations (Akinmulegun, 2012). For instance, Abu et al. (2018) provide empirical evidence on linking of the effectiveness of audit committees to the characteristics of the committee of a company. Prior empirical research such as the studies of Nazari, et al. (2020), Zaitul and Ilona (2018), Eyenubo et al., (2017) stated the characteristics of the audit committee as; committee size, committee independence, committee diligence, committee gender, committee financial expertise. According to Ezeokoli et al., (2019) audit committee size (ACS) is measured as the number of boards of directors and shareholders appointed to be members of the audit committee of a company. It is documented that the size of the audit committee determines the direction of the audit report lag of a company which makes it difficult to apply their conclusions to listed industrial products enterprises in Nigeria.

This study, which looks at the determinants of profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria, is being conducted against this background with the prospect of the audit committee number audit committee composition and managerial share ownership because the study tries to analyse each as an individual determinant of profitability in industrial goods firms. And as a result, bridge the variable inclusion and sector gaps.

The main objective of the study is to assess the determinants of profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. In order to do this, others objectives include;

- i. Assess the effect of audit committee number of meetings on profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.
- ii. Assess the effect of managerial share ownership on profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.
- iii. Assess the effect of audit committee composition of meetings on profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Profitability

Profitability, which is frequently used as measure of financial performance, is one of the main objectives for the existence of many companies. Profit is an essential prerequisite for any company operating in today's increasingly competitive and globalized market. In addition, profit does not only serve as a means of attraction to investors; it also improves the level of solvency, and thus, strengthens consumers' confidence (Pandey, 2010). Alkhazaleh and Almsafir, (2014) define profitability as the level to which an organization can successfully and efficiently make the most of its obtainable funds and assets, and alter them into outstanding profit. This forms the basis for boosting income of employees, providing better quality products for customers, and having better environment friendly production units. Furthermore, higher earnings result in higher future investments, which creates more job opportunities and boosts people's income.

Audit Committee Composition

Audit committee composition refers to the makeup and characteristics of the members who serve on an audit committee, which is a subcommittee of a company's board of directors (Kidmat & Rehman 2014). The audit committee is in charge of managing the financial reporting process, internal controls, and the organization's audit function (Aqsa & Ghulam 2014). The form and membership of an audit committee are defined by a board of directors as a body constituted to manage an organization's financial reporting and audit processes (Marozva, 2015). The specific requirements for audit committee composition may vary depending on applicable laws, regulations, and corporate governance guidelines in different jurisdictions (Johl, Kaur & Cooper 2015). However, there are some common principles and best practices that guide the composition of audit committees.

Ho₁: Audit committee number of meetings has no significant effect on profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Managerial Share Ownership

Managerial share ownership refers to the ownership of company shares by managers or executives within an organization (Bulan, Sanyal & Yan 2009). It represents the extent to which managers have invested their personal funds in the company they work for, aligning their financial interests with those of the shareholders (Niresh & Velnampy 2014). Managerial share ownership is often seen as a positive corporate governance practice as it can have several potential benefits such as when managers have a significant stake in the company through share ownership, their financial well-being becomes tied to the efficiency and prosperity of the organisation (Bashar & Islam, 2014). This symmetry of interests can incentivise management to make decisions that are in the greatest beneficial of the company and its shareholders.

Ho₂: Managerial share ownership has no significant effect on profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria

Audit Committee Number of Meetings

The degree of activity performed by the audit committee is defined by the audit committee meeting. According to Al-Matari, Al-Swidi, Fadzil, and Al-Matari (2015), the variety of audit committee meetings held in a given year is related to the number of audit committee meetings held. An audit committee is a branch of the board of directors that controls the accuracy of the

financial reporting and disclosure (Aparna, 2015). The committee aids the board of directors in the duties of oversight for an entity's financial reporting, internal control system, risk management system, and both internal and external audit functions (Devi & Devi, 2014). The audit committee meeting is a critical feature of the audit committee.

Ho₃: Audit committee composition has no significant effect on profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Review of Empirical Studies

Many studies have been undertaken in Nigeria to study the drivers of profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria

In a recent study, Adegbe and Adekoya (2022) assess the impact of firm-specific factors, industry-specific factors, and macroeconomic factors on profitability. They discovered the firm size, leverage, liquidity, and market concentration were significant firm-specific determinants, while industry concentration and exchange rate volatility were significant industry-specific determinants. Macroeconomic factors such as inflation and GDP growth were also found to have a significant impact on profitability. Therefore, the previous study operationalizes on the proxies of firm size, leverage, liquidity, and market concentration. While, this study operationalizes on the proxies of audit committee number, audit committee composition and managerial share ownership which enables the bridge the variable inclusion gap.

In 2021, Oluwatobi et al. Investigated a study on the determinants of profitability in Nigeria's industrial goods sector. panel data regression analysis was use in the study and foundout that firm size, liquidity, and leverage had a significant positive relationship with profitability. However, the study found that asset turnover had a negative relationship with profitability. The study concluded that industrial goods firms could improve their profitability by increasing their size, maintaining high levels of liquidity and leverage, and managing their assets effectively. Therefore, the previous study operationalizes on the proxies of firm size, leverage and liquidity. While, this study operationalizes on the proxies of audit committee number, audit committee composition and managerial share ownership which enables the bridge the variable inclusion gap.

Another study by Adegbaju, Ologunde, and Adegbaju (2020) examined the impact of firm size on profitability in Nigeria's industrial goods sector. The study used regression analysis and found that there was a positive relationship between firm size and profitability. The study concluded that larger firms were more profitable than smaller firms. Therefore, the previous study operationalizes on the proxy of firm size. While, this study operationalizes on the proxies of audit committee number, audit committee composition and managerial share ownership which enables the bridge the variable inclusion gap.

A study by Ogunmuyiwa and Alege (2019) assess the impact of capital structure on the profitability of listed firms in Nigeria's industrial goods sector. The study used regression analysis and found that there was a significant positive relationship between leverage and profitability. The study concluded that industrial goods firms could improve their profitability by taking on more debt. Therefore, the previous study operationalizes on the proxy of leverage. While, this study operationalizes on the proxies of audit committee number, audit committee composition and managerial share ownership which enables the bridge the variable inclusion gap.

According to Adegbe and Fakile (2019), firm size, leverage, and liquidity significantly impact profitability. Similarly, Odeleye et al. (2019) found that leverage, liquidity, and firm size were

significant determinants of profitability. Olufemi and Adegbe (2020) also found that firm size, leverage, and liquidity had a significant impact on profitability, but added that corporate governance and market concentration were also important determinants. Therefore, the previous study operationalizes on the proxies of firm size, leverage liquidity and market concentration. While, this study operationalizes on the proxies of audit committee number, audit committee composition and managerial share ownership which enables the bridge the variable inclusion gap. In contrast, Ogunleye and Olokoyo (2019) found that firm size, leverage, and liquidity have no meaningful impact on profitability. Instead, they found that asset tangibility, sales growth, and market share were the primary profit drivers. Therefore, the previous study operationalizes on the proxies of firm size, leverage, liquidity, asset tangibility, sales growth, and market share. While, this study operationalizes on the proxies of audit committee number, audit committee composition and managerial share ownership which enables the bridge the variable inclusion gap.

Likewise, Ajide and Alimi (2020) found that market concentration, asset tangibility, and sales growth were significant determinants of profitability, while liquidity and leverage had no significant impact.

Ogiriki, Andabai, and Bina (2018), who used the Ordinary Least Squares regression to examine financial leverage and its effect on corporate performance of firms in Nigeria from 1999 to 2016, long-term debt, return on asset, and return on equity was adopted as dependent and explanatory variables, respectively (OLS). The findings shows that ROA and ROE had a significant positive effect on firms' long-term debt. The study concluded that financial leverage has a significant influence on the corporate performance of Nigerian firms and recommended effective long-term management debts. Therefore, the previous study operationalizes on the proxies of long-term debt, return on asset, and return on equity. While, this study operationalizes on the proxies of audit committee number, audit committee composition and managerial share ownership which enables the bridge the variable inclusion gap.

Theoretical Review

This study's theoretical review examines signalling theory as fundamental theory to describe profitability concept of the study.

The Market Power Theory

Bain and Company developed market power theory (1951). According to this theory, a rise in the market power leads to either a monopoly or revenues (Athanasoglou, Brissimis & Delis, 2005). The theory is based on the premise that market concentration is the best indicator of market power because more focused markets exhibit superior market shortcomings, allowing various enterprises to set prices for their goods and services at levels that are less advantageous to their clients or customers (Punt & Rooij, 2001). The theory also states that firms with a significant market share and well-differentiated products and services can actually earn monopolistic profits and succeed or win against competitors (Nkegbe & Yazidu, 2015).

The market power theory holds that increased market concentration makes it possible for companies to collaborate and earn significant incremental profits as a result of the firm's investment of different products and services, which also increases market share and market power in predicting product prices (Mirzaei, 2012). The market-power theory also asserts that Market power constitutes one of the most important variables influencing profitability, and that

concentrated markets generally involve shortcomings caused by collusion, which is enabled by market concentration, and by respective statutory barriers to entry or exit (Punt & Rooij, 2001).

Market power theory is used in industrial goods companies to describe firm profitability and how market share affects it. The theory discusses the key relationship between the size of a firm and its financial performance. According to market power theory, an organisation's profitability is determined by the industry's market structure (Onuonga, 2014). Furthermore, this theory contends that the market structure of companies determines firm profitability (Ntow & Laryea, 2012). According to Obumuyi (2013), this theory states that firm profitability is a function of external market factors, and that industry structure, as measured by market concentration in terms of the market share ratio, affects firm profitability (Fisseha, 2015).

Most managers intend to achieve positive outcomes and a solid reputation by increasing disclosure, which may enhance the firm's value and profitability (Muzahem, 2011). The study is based on the market power theory, which holds that increased profits result from higher market concentration, which enable industries to work hand in hand and earn maximum profit due to the firm's portfolio of different products and services, which also rises market share and market power in indicating product prices.

3 METHODOLOGY

The study examined the determinants that affect the profitability of Nigerian listed industrial goods companies. The study used descriptive research. As a result, a descriptive design assisted in determining the factors that influence the profitability of Nigeria Listed Industrial Goods Companies in Nigeria.

The study population are the listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria as at December, 2022 which are listed in the Nigeria Exchange Group. This study population consists of 13 (thirteen) listed Industrial Goods companies in Nigeria. These include; Austin Laz & Company Plc, Berger Paints Plc, Beta Glass Plc, BUA Cement Plc, CAP Plc, Cutix PLC, Dangote Cement Plc, Greif Nigeria Plc, Lafarge Africa Plc, Meyer Plc, Notore Chemicals Ind. Ltd., Premier Paints Plc, Tripple Gee and Company Plc. This population had the propensity to provide pertinent information on profitability determinants.

Model Specifications

The regression model is employed to assess the relationship between the variables studied, which comprises;

Independent variables such as; Managerial Shared Ownership, Audit Committee Composition and Audit Committee Meetings.

Dependent variable: Profitability (Return on Assets).

The regression model looked like this:

$$PRT_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 MSO_{it} + \beta_2 ACC_{it} + \beta_3 ACM_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ Magaretha and Supertika (2016)}$$

Where as;

PRT = Profitability

MSO= Managerial Shared Ownership

ACC = Audit Committee Composition

ACM = Audit Committee Meetings

ε = Error Term

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Coefficients of the Variables

3.4 Table 1. Variables Definition, Measurements and Source

Variable Acronym	Variable Name	Variable Measurement
ROA	Return on Assets	Dependent Profit before interest and tax/total assets Burja (2011), Magaretha and Supertika (2016)
ACM	Audit Committee meetings	Independent No of audit committee meetings held per year Al-Matari, Al-Swidi, Fadzil and Al-Matari (2015)
ACC	Audit Committee Composition	This is the proportion of non-executive directors to the total audit committee members (Garko, 2015).
MSO	Managerial share ownership	Number of shares by directors on the board to the total number of outstanding shares (Akpan, 2015).

Source; Author' Compilation, 2023

Methods of Data Collection

The study entails the be use of secondary data from annual published financial statements of all Listed Industrial Goods companies in Nigeria from December 31, 2013 to December 31, 2022. The data would cover a ten-year period, from 2013 to 2022. Data from financial statements was deemed reliable because financial statements are prepared in every organization in accordance with standardised accounting principles. Taking into account the prevailing Covid-19 pandemic and the containment measures were in place, the researcher would be biased to using mailed, company portal and Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG) sources.

Data analysis encompasses inspecting the obtained data and drawing conclusions and inferences. The collected data will be modified and organised for comprehensiveness before being analysed adopting ordinary least squares (OLS) and Pearson correlation using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). Utilizing descriptive and inferential statistics, the SPSS statistical software or tool would be used to analyse the data collected. Correlation and regression analysis were among the inferential statistics that was utilize. The results would be presented using tables, charts, and graphs and accompanied by a narrative of the statistics.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section evaluates and statistically evaluates the data gathered for the investigation. The section opens with descriptive statistics and a correlation matrix. It then gives the regression outcomes and evaluates the findings in accordance with past research.

Descriptive Statistics

The summary of the descriptive statistics of the variables are presented in table 2.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
ROA	0.12058	0.307986	0.1308471	.0998828
ACM	10	19	14.13889	2.427848
ACC	0.3571	0.90909	0.5654167	0.1449466
MSO	3	7	5.777778	0.7968191

SOURCE: SPSS Output, 2023

From table 2, the minimum and maximum rate of return on asset are 0.12058 and 0.307986 respectively. A higher return on asset indicates improved financial success, whereas a lower return on asset indicates negative financial performance. The average return on asset is 0.1308471 which implies that the average financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria is N130m. Audit committee meeting shows minimum and maximum values of 10 and 19 respectively. This implies that for firms to attain minimum and maximum financial performance they must have meeting of 10 and 19 respectively. The average meeting position of the firms is 14.13889. This means that for the firms to perform averagely, they must maintain an average meeting position of 14.

Audit committee composition shows minimum and maximum values of 0.3571 and 0.90909 respectively. This indicates that for firms to have minimum financial performance they must have net profit margin of 36% and for maximum financial performance, the firm should have a net profit margin of 91%. The average value of the audit composition is 0.5654167, which means that for the industrial goods firms to maintain average financial performance the most maintain 57% of net profit margin.

Managerial Share ownership revealed minimum and maximum values of 3 and 7 respectively. This implies for the industrial goods firms to have a minimum financial performance, their MSO should be less than 3 and to maintain a maximum performance their MSO should not exceed 7.

Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix explains the degree of link between the study's dependent and independent variables, and also the correlation between the independent variables. Table 3 summarises the study's variables' relationships.

Table 3 Correlation Matrix

Variables	ROA	ACM	ACC	MSO
ROA	1.0000			
ACM	0.1697	1.0000		
ACC	0.0222	0.5760	1.0000	
MSO	0.1788	0.4908	0.0607	1.0000

SOURCE: STATA Output, 2023

According to Table 3, audit committee meetings are favourably and profoundly linked with return on asset. The data also reveals that the makeup of the audit committee is favourably associated to return on asset. The variable has a significant association at the 5% level of significance. And

management share ownership has a considerable positive correlation with return on asset with a value of 0.1788.

The association between the independent variables reveals that ACM and ACC are positively associated and significant. And MSO has a considerable positive correlation with ACM. MSO has a positive correlation with ACC of 0.0607, which is significant at the 10% level of significance.

Discussion of Findings and Analysis of Regression Results

Given the data's nature, both definitive effect and random effect models were examined. The Hausman specification test was then employed to distinguish between the two outcomes. This suggests that the random effect was chosen as the best estimator by the test. In addition, for the random effect, the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test was used to determine whether there is a panel effect between the variables that warrants the use of Generalised Least Square or not, resulting in the implementation of Pooled Ordinary Least Square regression.

The hettest revealed a Chi2 value of 0.87 with a p-value of 0.3500, and the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test for random effect revealed a Chi2 value of 0.00 with a p-value of 1.000, which is not considered statistically significant according to the results attached as appendix (II H). The robust GLS had a Chi2 of 0.435 and a p-value of 0.000. The GLS robust is being employed in this investigation.

Table 4 summarises the generalised least square robust regression results obtained from the study's model.

Table 4 Regression Results

Variables	Coefficient	T-Values	P-Values
Constant	0.4436562	0.29	0.0774
ACM	0.1416064	0.55	0.0582
ACC	0.0120326	0.21	0.0833
MSO	0.0035751	0.17	0.0867
R²	0.24084		
Wald Chi²	0.435		
Prob. Chi²			0.000

SOURCE: STATA Output, 2023

Table 4 demonstrate that the functional relationship between the dependent and independent variables is:

$$ROA = 0.4436562 + 0.1416064GPM + 0.0120326NPM + 0.0035751IFRS$$

The table shows that ACM has positive significant impact on the financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This can be observed from the computed value of beta coefficient of 0.1416064 with p-value of 0.0582 which is statistically significant.

The table also revealed that ACC is positively and significantly impacting on the financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The beta coefficient of the variables is -0.0120326 and the p-value is 0.0833 which is significant. This study is consistent with the conclusions drawn by Yermack (2016).

The table also reveals a positive significant relationship between MSO and the financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. From the result, the beta coefficient is 0.0035751 and the p-value is 0.0867 which is insignificant.

The combined and overall effect of the predictor factors on the explained variable demonstrated that the model is appropriate and error-free. The Wald Chi² value of 0.435 with a Prob. Chi² of 0.0000, which is significant at the 1% level of significance, indicates that the model is well matched with the study's variables. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination R² (0.24%) represents the proportion of the total variance in the dependent variable (return on asset) explained by the independent variables (audit committee meeting, audit committee composition, and managerial share ownership). This means that the cumulative effect of audit committee meetings accounts for 0.24% of the total variation in financial performance of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. audit committee composition and managerial share ownership.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Profit reveals the degree of efficiency with which a company unit uses resources, making it a good measure of how effective a business unit is. The efficiency of the business unit will increase as profit increases. The study therefore concludes that, audit committee meeting has a positive and significant impact on the financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Audit committee composition is positively and significantly impacting on the financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. And managerial share ownership is positively significant to the financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

From the result, the recommends that:

Before deciding on borrowed financing, Nigerian industrial products enterprises should assess the prospective economic benefits versus the expense. When it is clear that increasing debt will impair profitability, other sources of capital, such as equity capital, should be considered.

The government should actively invest in the assets of large industrial goods enterprises since larger industrial goods firms have a better profit margin. Such businesses can readily take advantage of economies of scale to reduce costs and, eventually, profit.

To maximise profitability, industrial products enterprises in Nigeria must build a proper cash flow mix. Industrial products enterprises in Nigeria must design several methods for selecting the most beneficial components of its cash flows for use in operations in order to increase profitability.

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